

INVESTIGATION ON MICROSTRUCTURES OF LANXIDE $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al}$ CERAMIC COMPOSITES AND THEIR GROWTH BEHAVIORS

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ABSTRACT

Lanxide $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3/\text{Al}$ ceramic composites are fabricated by the direct oxidation of molten aluminum alloy with air. The microstructures of three types of Lanxide materials have been studied. It has been discovered for the first time that there are mainly two kinds of growth manners in which Lanxide materials grow or develop. Growing cell model can be adopted to describe the growth behaviors of Lanxide materials. The relationship among the microstructure, growth manner and flexural strength of composites is discussed.

KEYWORDS: Composites; Matrix / Ceramic; Formation / Matrix / Oxidation; Mechanism; Microstructures.

1. INTRODUCTION

Lanxide process is one of the most attractive techniques for fabricating advanced ceramic composite materials owing to its beneficial features, such as the ease of fabrication, ability to tailor materials properties, projected low costs and promising commercialization. This novel process invented by Lanxide Corporation results in a variety of unique ceramic composites called Lanxide materials by direct oxidizing aluminum alloy with gaseous oxidants such as oxygen in air^(1, 2). Our current work is concerned with describing the characteristics of Lanxide materials, suggesting the growth behaviors and discussing the relationship of strength with microstructures.

2. PREPARATION OF EXPERIMENTAL MATERIALS

The formation of Lanxide materials involves the oxidation of molten aluminum alloy by oxygen in atmosphere. The process is schematically illustrated in Fig.1. Al-Si-Mg alloy was employed as parent metal for producing Lanxide materials, containing 7.60 wt% silicon and 2.93wt% magnesium. Under appropriate conditions, usually at the temperature ranging from 500°C to 800°C above aluminum melting point, the Lanxide material initially forms on melt's surfaces exposed to air and progressively grows outward from the original metal surfaces. The growth of Lanxide material is maintained by wicking molten aluminum alloy through microscopic channels in reaction product to

arrive the growing front surface contacting with air as the oxidation continues. Reinforcements or fillers can be readily incorporated into Lanxide matrix by simply allowing the Lanxide material to grow or penetrate into the filler bed so as to produce ceramic composites.

Fig.1 Schematic of Lanxide process

There were three types of Lanxide materials prepared for this study, hereinafter designating A, B and C. The experimental conditions are listed in table 1. The SiC particle used for Material C was commercial grade abrasive grain about $14\mu\text{m}$ in mean size. The prepared set-up shown in Fig.1 was put into a resistant heating furnace for processing in ambient atmosphere. It began with a 5-hour heating period from room temperature to growth temperature or set-point, such as 1200°C or 1400°C . Then the set-up was hold at growth temperature for the formation of Lanxide material, which took usually 24 hours or longer, depending upon the process conditions. After being cooled down to room temperature inside the furnace, the Lanxide samples removed from furnace were sectioned along the growth direction, then shaped, ground and polished for analyses and/or strength tests. All the Lanxide materials grew upward in this study.

TABLE 1 EXPERIMENTAL CONDITIONS FOR PREPARING LANXIDE MATERIALS

materials	conditions	growth temperature	fillers	parent metal
A		1400°C	None	7.60wt% Si, 2.93wt% Mg Al (balance)
B		1200°C	None	
C		1200°C	SiC($\sim 14\mu\text{m}$)	

3. MICROSTRUCTURES OF LANXIDE MATERIALS

The analyses of Lanxide materials were conducted on the surfaces oriented parallel to the growth direction. The microstructures, phase constitutions and chemical compositions of Lanxide materials were investigated by opticle microscopic analysis of ceramographically prepared crosssection, X-ray diffractometry, SEM and EPMA.

Lanxide materials are of complex microstructures. X-ray diffraction shows that the new composites consist of α - Al_2O_3 , aluminum, silicon and a minor amount of spinel, which is consistent with the work of Newkirk et al ⁽²⁾. Fig.2 shows the typical microstructure of Lanxide materials. Opticle microscopic analysis, SEM and EPMA reveal that the skeleton α - Al_2O_3 serves as matrix (gray phase) containing various dispersions of aluminum alloy (bright phase) and / or pores (dark phase). The skeletal structure of α - Al_2O_3 matrix is well demonstrated in Fig.3. Both the metal constituents and voids can be either interconnected in all three dimensions or isolated, depending upon the processing conditions.

Fig.2 Typical microstructure of Lanxide material

Fig.3 Elevated morphology of α - Al_2O_3 skeleton near porous area

Further examination shows that there are three types of zones with different structures for Material A shown in Fig.4. Obviously the morphology changes in two converse tendencies along the growth direction (from bottom to top of specimen): a) The metal phases get more and more interconnected accompanying with the accumulation of Si phase; b) Interconnected pores gradually tend to be isolated and the porosity decreases. Structure in Fig.4(b), corresponding to middle part of specimen, represents a typical morphology of Lanxide material. The pores appear to be a network dividing Lanxide matrix into a cellular structure. Inside the cells, it tends to be a 3:2:0 composite ⁽³⁾ with a part of metallic phases being interconnected and part being isolated. Few pore is dispersed in cell interior. Therefore, it can be understood that the over-development of network of pores results in the porous structure in bottom of specimen, which eliminates the cellular feature of structure. Similarly, the well-developed metal network may lead to structure in Fig.4(C), from which the cellular structure constructed by metal network can still be noticed.

Fig.4 Change of microstructures of Material A along the growth direction (from bottom to top)

- (a) bottom
- (b) middle
- (c) top

Material B gets more uniform microstructure shown in Fig.5. High porosity (24.8 vol%) makes the cellular structure irregular. The interconnected pores are similar to those in Fig.4(a) (bottom of specimen). But the metal network can only be found in growth front within millimetre scale regions.

Fig.5 Microstructure of Material B

Fig.6 Microstructure of Material C

The microstructure of Lanxide material filled with reinforcement is vastly different. As shown in Fig.6, Material C can be distinguished from the prior types of Lanxide materials in following aspects. Firstly, the major difference is that the porosity reduces dramatically (as low as 0.4 vol%) and the void tends to close up. Secondly, higher fraction of metallic constituents is noticed due to the uncomplete oxidation. Thirdly, the metal phases interconnect to a greater degree and show a tendency of clustering. Few pore can be observed at the interfaces of SiC grain with matrix, which may lead to the conclusion that SiC particles are well combined with matrix.

4. GROWTH BEHAVIORS OF LANXIDE MATERIALS

Newkirk et al ⁽⁴⁾ have proposed a mechanism explaining why the rapid oxidation process occurs by the continuous wicking of molten metal through the microchannels in reaction product. But how the Lanxide materials grow or develop still remains a problem. In this paper, a "growing cell" model is suggested to describe the growth behaviors of Lanxide materials.

As mentioned above, the formation of Lanxide materials can be pertinently described as a growth procedure. The growth behavior is characterized by the close resemblance to the growth of bush or tree, which is typically illustrated in Fig.7. The term "growing cell" is introduced to describe the growth as basic structural element or unit. Obviously, the growing cell is similar to a single bush, the growing front is like to the crown of bush or tree, and the micro-channels resemble the stems which also transport the needs for maintaining the growth. Thus, a huge number of growing cells or bushes make up the bulk body of Lanxide material. The intervals among growing cells construct the voids or pores shown in Fig.7, which results in the cellular structure mentioned hereinbefore.

Fig.7 A typical example illustrating the growth behaviors of Lanxide materials

There are two types of manners in which Lanxide materials grow: i) even growth and ii) uneven growth, which means respectively the growing front are "even" and "uneven". The so called "even" and "uneven" are stated in the macroscale dimension. At the initial stage of growth, many growing cells form on the surface of parent metal ingot where it is allowed to grow upward. As the oxidation continues, the growing cells develop gradually, and / or new growing cells are born on the formed ones. In this way, the growing front progresses upward. If the growing cells constructing the growing front have approximately the dimension of same order, it is regarded that the growth of Lanxide material belongs to "even growth" manner, in another words, the growing front is even. If not, Lanxide material grows in uneven growth manner, or the growing front is uneven. Fig.8 shows the morphologies of growing front surfaces corresponding to two types of growth manners by SEM, demonstrating the cellular feature of growing fronts. It is easily found the uneven growth manner presents more cellular structure than even growth manner does. But the latter is more uniform in cell size than the former. A polished crosssection shown in Fig.9 dramatically demonstrates the growth procedure of Lanxide material or the upward movement of growing front surfaces. It should be noted that Fig.9 is just a example specially chosen for illustrating the growth or formation of Lanxide

body. Usually, the development of growing cells leads to much more uniform structure than in Fig.9 although the growth does not always follow the fixed growth manner during the formation of whole Lanxide body.

(a) even growth

(b) uneven growth

Fig.8 SEM shows morphology of two types of growth manners on growing front surfaces

Fig.9 The growth process of Lanxide body

5. DISCUSSION

Attempt was made to understand the relationship among growth manner, microstructure and flexural strength. It is not far to seek the reasons resulting in the cellular microstructure in Material A and B, i.e., they all stem from the pile of growing cells. The interconnected pores come from the intervals among the growing cells or Lanxide matrix. In Material C, the cellular feature disappears because particles incorporated disturb the full development of growing cells. In another words, the growing cells are forced to grow within the intervals among particles. The dimension of such intervals is so small (compared with growing cells) that the growing cells are too tinny to be cellular. In fact the growing front moves upward in a very even manner. Hence, porosity of Material C can be as low as 0.4 vol%.

The fact that Material A appears in different microstructures along growth direction can be explained by: i) The molten aluminum filled in the microchannels at bottom of specimen is further drained out by wicking effect for growth after the parent metal ingot is exhausted, which may cause the highly porous structure in Fig.4 (a); ii) The molten metals remaining still in the microchannels at top of specimen after cooling form the network of metallic constituents in Fig.4(c), rather than network of voids as in Fig.4(a).

The flexural strength was measured in three-point bending with the length of specimens oriented perpendicular to the growth direction. The specimens were bars 3.0mm thick, 4mm wide and about 40mm long. The tests were all performed at a crosshead speed of $8.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$. The testing results show the flexural strengths of Material B and C at room temperature are 78MPa and 394MPa, respectively. Each value represents a result obtained from a single specimen. The experimental results can be explained straightforwardly by their microstructures, especially the pores and reinforcements. Material B contains much higher porosity (24.8 vol%) than Material C. What is more, the pores are interconnected, tortuous and sharp in shape which may result in high level of stress concentration. In Material C, reinforcement SiC particles contribute considerably to the enhancement of strength. Low porosity (0.4 vol%) and close-up structures of voids degrade the strength to much lower extent. Even the residual metallic constituents which may be partially exhausted to form pores can both toughen and strengthen Material C. Thus, the flexural strength is increased remarkably.

According to the classification of growth manner, the growth of Material B belongs to uneven growth and growth of Material C belongs to even growth. In general speaking, uneven growth produces highly porous structure. Material A and B are some of examples. Even growth usually results in dense structure such as Material C. It is easy to conclude that controlling the growth manner is one of the effective ways to tailor both the microstructure and strength of Lanxide material. How to control the growth manner and what exactly occurs in the growth of Lanxide material will be disclosed in our future papers.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The novel Lanxide process has brought about new materials different from the conventional ceramic composites in both microstructures and properties. The mechanism of Lanxide technique, basing on the newly-discovered oxidation phenomenon of molten metals, is characterized by the unique growth manners resembling to those of bush or tree in nature. Either the microstructures or strengths can be understood by tracing back to the growth manners by which various Lanxide materials have

been historically developed.

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